

STUDIES IN VITAMIN-C OXIDATION. PART I. CO-EXISTENCE OF OXIDISING AND PROTECTIVE FACTORS IN PLANTS FOR VITAMIN-C.

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The existence of a protective factor in vegetables, which protects vitamin-C from oxidation has been established. The enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase and the protective factor occur together in various vegetables, and a method is described for the separation of the two factors from each other. The protective factor inhibits the copper oxidation, while the enzymic oxidation of the vitamin is not influenced by it. The enzyme and the protective factor are more concentrated in the pericarp of the vegetables. The nature and properties of the protective factor have been investigated.

Although vitamin-C is very easily oxidised, particularly in presence of extremely minute amounts of copper, it occurs exclusively in the reduced state in fresh vegetables. It would appear, therefore, that there must be some mechanism in vegetables, which prevents the oxidation of the vitamin. Although the existence of such protective mechanism has been established in animal tissues (De Caro and Giani, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, 228, 13; Mawson, *Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 569; Giri, *Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 309; Giri and Shourie, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1940, 27, 685), in plants, however, it has not been shown to be of such wide occurrence.

Since many vegetables contain appreciable amounts of copper, it was of considerable interest to find out whether there exists any protective mechanism which prevents the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin by copper. In the present paper the existence of a protective mechanism for the non-enzymic oxidation of vitamin-C in vegetables is established, and the isolation, nature and properties of the protective constituents form the subject matter of the investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The rate of oxidation of vitamin-C was followed both manometrically and titrimetrically. To each manometric vessel were added to the main chamber: (1) 1 c.c. of *M*/15-phosphate buffer, pH 5.9, (2) 0.5 c.c. of copper sulphate solution (containing 7 mg. of copper sulphate), (3) 1 c.c. of water or the solution containing the protective factor. The side-bulb contained 0.5 ml. (2 mg.) vitamin-C solution. Potassium hydroxide filter papers

were placed in the central well. Air filled the gas space and the temperature was 30°. The vitamin solution was tipped in when the vessels were placed in the bath and the temperature equilibrium was reached and the oxygen uptake was measured for a 45 minute period. Glass distilled water was used throughout these experiments.

The rate of oxidation of vitamin-C was followed titrimetrically by titrating the vitamin with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol.

Separation of the Protective Factors for Vitamin-C Oxidation free from the Ascorbic Acid Oxidase.

The existence in vegetables of a specific enzyme "Ascorbic acid oxidase" which is responsible for the oxidation of vitamin-C has been established by a number of workers Chakrabarty and Guba (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 839) have investigated the distribution of the enzyme in various Indian fruits and vegetables, and have shown that the enzyme occurs in various vegetables. It is probable that the effect of the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase present in vegetables may outweigh the action of the protective constituents present in them, so that the influence of the latter on vitamin-C oxidation may not be apparent, when both of them occur together. Hence it would appear that the failure of previous workers to observe any significant amount of protective substances in vegetables is to be ascribed to the occurrence of ascorbic acid oxidase in association with the protective substances, and without separating the enzyme from the protective constituents, the detection of the latter would not be possible. A method for the separation of the enzyme and the protective constituents from one another is described below.

The expressed juice of the vegetables, cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*), pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*), ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula*), snake gourd (*Tricosanthus anguina*), bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia*), and *Amaranthus* was the starting material for the preparation of the enzyme and the protective factor.

Preparation of an Extract containing the Protective Factors.—To the juice obtained by pressing the pulp of the pericarp of the vegetable, after centrifuging, was added an equal volume of acetone, and the precipitate formed was removed by centrifugation. The clear aqueous-acetone solution was kept on the water-bath, until the solution was completely freed from acetone. This aqueous extract contains the protective substances which inhibit the oxidation of the vitamin both in presence and absence of copper. This will be designated as the protective factor (P. F.) for vitamin-C.

Preparation of the Enzyme.—The precipitate obtained after the addition of acetone contained the enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase. It was dispersed

in the same volume of water as the original juice, centrifuged to remove the suspended matter, and used for the determination of the activity of the enzyme.

Determination of the Activity of the Enzyme, Ascorbic Acid Oxidase and the Influence of the Protective Factor on Vitamin-C Oxidation.

The reaction mixtures in each case consisted of 5 mg. of ascorbic acid in 20 c.c. of *M/5*-acetic acid-acetate buffer (p_H 5.6). The total volume of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 30 c.c. 2 C.c. of the enzyme and 2 c.c. of the solution containing the protective factor were added to the reaction mixture for determining the activity of the enzyme and the protective action of the acetone extract. The solutions were adjusted to the required p_H before mixing. The controls contained the same amount of vitamin-C without the addition of the protective factor. Immediately after the addition of the vitamin, $\frac{1}{2}$ c.c. samples of each solution were delivered into a series of beakers, each containing 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid in order to arrest the oxidation, and immediately titrated with the indophenol dye. The volume of the titre, thus obtained, gave the concentration of the vitamin at the beginning of the reaction. At stated intervals of time aliquots were removed and titrated similarly.

Effect of the Protective Factor isolated from Vegetables on the Oxidation of Vitamin-C in the absence of Cu^{++} and of Ascorbic Acid Oxidase.

The results of experiments on the influence of protective factor isolated from various vegetables according to the method described above, on the oxidation of vitamin-C are presented in Table I.

TABLE I
Oxidation of vitamin-C

$p_H=5.6$. Temp. = 37° . Total volume of the reaction mixture = 30 c.c. (20 c.c. of *M/5*-acetate buffer, V. C. = 5 c.c.; 1 c.c. of P. F.)

Time (min.)	Vitamin-C and protective factor from															
	V. C.		<i>Cucumis sativus.</i>		<i>Cucurbita maxima.</i>		<i>Luffa acutangula.</i>		<i>Morinda charantia.</i>		<i>Amaranthus.</i>		<i>Tricosanthes anguina.</i>		V. C.	
	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.	V. C. oxidised.
0	5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.	
10	4.11	18%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%	5.0	0%
20	3.52	30	5.0	0	5.0	0	5.0	0	5.0	0	5.0	0	5.0	0	5.0	0
30	3.13	38	4.9	2	4.9	2	5.0	0	4.89	4	4.72	6	5.0	0		
60	2.54	50	4.7	6	4.8	4	4.6	8	4.66	8	4.72	6	5.0	0		

V. C. = vitamin-C; P. F. = the extract containing the protective factor. Similar results were obtained at the alkaline p_H 7.2.

Effect of the Protective Factor on the Catalytic Oxidation of Vitamin C in presence of added Cu^{++} .

(a) *Oxidation followed by Titration.*—The results obtained on the effect of the protective factor obtained from various vegetables, on the oxidation of vitamin-C in presence of added Cu^{++} are presented in Table II.

TABLE II.

Oxidation of vitamin-C.

Temp. = 37°; p_H = 5.6; Total volume of reaction mixture, 30 c.c. 20 c.c. acetate buffer, 1 c.c. $CuSO_4$ (0.014 mg. $CuSO_4$); 5 c.c. V. C. (5 mg.); x c.c. of P. F. ($x = 2$ or 5).

Vitamin-C, copper ion and protective factor (P. F.) from

Time (min.)	V. C.+Cu		(2 c.c.) <i>C. sativus</i> .		(5 c.c.) <i>C. maxima</i> .		(5 c.c.) <i>M. charantia</i> .		(5 c.c.) <i>T. anguina</i> .	
	V. C.	V. C. oxidis- ed.	V. C.	V. C. oxidis- ed.	V. C.	V. C. oxidis- ed.	V. C.	V. C. oxidis- ed.	V. C.	V. C. oxidis- ed.
0	5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.		5.0 mg.	
10	2.68	48%	2.97	42%	4.8	6%	4.6	8%	3.96	22%
20	2.11	58	2.59	50	—	—	—	—	—	—
30	1.82	64	2.40	52	4.6	10	4.4	12	2.94	42
60	0.67	88	1.72	66	4.3	14	4.04	20	20.35	54

The results show that the protective factor, prepared from the vegetables, inhibits the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin by added Cu^{++} .

(b) *Oxidation followed Manometrically.*—The influence of the protective factor prepared from *Cucumis sativus* on the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} was studied manometrically. The results are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

Effect of protective factor on the oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu⁺⁺

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to vitamin C, vitamin C+Cu⁺⁺ and vitamin-C+Cu⁺⁺+protective factor.

It can be seen from the figure that the oxygen consumption of the system vitamin-C+Cu+protective factor is much less than that of vitamin-C+Cu system, thereby showing that the factor exerts powerful protection against the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin by Cu⁺⁺

Study of the Distribution of the Ascorbic Acid Oxidase and the Protective Factor in Vegetables.

Each vegetable was divided into the following portions:

- (a) The outermost portion (pericarp, representing a layer of about 1/4 cm. thickness from the surface, together with the skin),
- (b) The middle portion (representing the next immediate layer of about 1 cm. thickness), and
- (c) The innermost portion (representing the remaining part of the vegetable, the core)

These different parts of the vegetable were mashed well and the juice expressed separately. The enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, and the protective factor were isolated from the juice, and their effect on the oxidation of vitamin-C was determined. The results are presented in Tables IIIA and IIIB.

TABLE IIIA.

Distribution of the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase in vegetables.

10 C.c. of *M*/5-acetate buffer, 5 mg. of vitamin-C, 1 c.c. of the enzyme solution taken. Total volume=30 c.c. Temperature=37°. p_H 5.6.

E_a , E_b and E_c represent the enzyme preparations obtained from pericarp, middle portion and innermost portion respectively, of each vegetable.

Time (min.)	<i>C. sativus.</i>				<i>C. maxima.</i>				<i>L. acutangula.</i>				<i>T. angulina</i>			
	%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.			
	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.
	+	+	+		+	+	+		+	+	+		+	+	+	
	E_a	E_b	E_c		E_a	E_b	E_c		E_a	E_b	E_c		E_a	E_b	E_c	
10	16	58	28	16	14	52	10	22	20	30	4	20	14	34	—	22
30	34	82	54	38	32	70	24	42	34	42	18	38	28	54	—	40
60	52	96	78	52	42	88	36	68	44	64	18	50	42	74	—	52

TABLE IIIB.

Distribution of the protective factor in vegetables.

Reaction mixture, same as in Table IIIA, with the addition of 1 c.c. of $CuSO_4$ solution (0.014 g. $CuSO_4$) and 1 c.c. of protective factor solution, instead of the enzyme.

P_a , P_b and P_c represent the protective factors isolated from the pericarp, middle portion, and innermost portion respectively, of each vegetable.

Time (min.)	<i>C. sativus.</i>				<i>C. maxima.</i>				<i>L. acutangula.</i>				<i>T. angulina.</i>			
	%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.				%Oxidation of V.C.			
	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.	V.C.
	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	
	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	P_a	P_b	P_c		P_a	P_b	P_c		P_a	P_b	P_c		P_a	P_b	P_c	
10	46	36	42	30	36	6	6	10	40	12	28	32	40	22	—	28
30	62	50	60	44	52	10	12	18	56	26	42	46	60	42	—	48
60	80	68	76	60	64	14	20	26	74	38	60	66	78	54	—	62

The results show that the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase is concentrated in the outer skin and the pericarp of the vegetables investigated. The protective factor also is more concentrated in the pericarp than in other portions of the vegetables.

Effect of the Protective Factor on the Enzymic Oxidation of Vitamin-C.

King and co-workers (Stotz, Harrer and King, *Science*, 1937, **86**, 35; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, **110**, 511) have shown that a number of inhibitors of copper catalysis of vitamin-C oxidation, exert similar inhibition of the activity of the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase, and concluded that the activity of the enzyme is due to the copper present in combination with protein material. Krishnamurthy and Giri (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1941 *in press*) have shown recently that pyrophosphate, which inhibits the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} , does not exert the same degree of inhibition on the enzymic oxidation of the vitamin. The question whether the protective factor isolated from the vegetables behaves similarly towards the enzymic oxidation of the vitamin was, therefore, investigated. The results of the experiments on the effect of the protective factor on the enzymic and Cu^{++} oxidation of the vitamin are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Reaction mixture: 10 c.c. acetate buffer; 1 c.c. of CuSO_4 (0.014 mg. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) or 1 c.c. enzyme; 5 c.c. of the protective factor from *Cucumis sativus*. Total volume = 31 c.c.

Time	%Oxidation of vitamin-C			
	V.C. + Cu	V.C. + Cu + P.F.	V.C. + En.	V.C. + En + P.F.
10 min.	38	20	48	50
30	56	40	72	78
60	74	50	92	96

The results show that the protective factor does not exert any significant degree of protection against the enzymic oxidation of vitamin-C.

D I S C U S S I O N.

The important point that emerges from the results reported in the present investigation is that there are certain constituents in vegetables, which protect vitamin-C from oxidation. These constituents, which are

designated as protective factors for vitamin-C, are widely distributed in vegetables and occur in association with the ascorbic acid oxidase. The two factors—the enzyme which oxidises vitamin-C, and the protective factor which inhibits the oxidation of the vitamin—have been separated from each other and the properties of the protective factor have been investigated.

The protective factor inhibits the non-enzymic oxidation of the vitamin both in presence and absence of added Cu^{++} . Both the enzyme and the protective factor are more concentrated in the pericarp of the vegetables investigated. Although the copper oxidation of the vitamin is inhibited, the enzymic oxidation is not affected to any appreciable extent by the factor.

The Nature of the Protective Factor.—The protective factor is thermostable and dialysable. A concentrated preparation of the factor can be obtained by evaporation on a water-bath, and the concentrated preparation retains the protective property in full.

Further examination of the nature of the constituents (from *Cucumis sativus*, *Cucurbita maxima*, and *Luffa acutangula*) which exert protective action, revealed that one of the important constituents was tartaric acid which exerts protective action on the vitamin. A detailed study of the results obtained on the protective action of tartaric acid and other constituents, which are widely distributed in plants, will be published in the succeeding paper of this series. The extract containing the protective factor gave also tests for reducing sugars. Although the presence of fructose was established by various specific tests, it does not exert any protective action on the vitamin. Further work on the chemical nature of the protective constituents is in progress.

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